

Substituent and Solvent Effects on Phenol-Isocyanate Reactions

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Manuscript received 14 November 1991, revised 31 March 1992, accepted 1 April 1992

The interaction of isocyanate with various hydroxylic and amine compounds has been the subject of study¹⁻³. This report describes the studies on the reaction of phenyl isocyanate with phenol, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresols in the presence of diethylcyclohexylamine (DECHA) and dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTDL).

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants and the activation parameters for the reaction of phenyl isocyanate with phenol, *o*-, *m* and *p*-cresols in the presence of the amine and tin catalysts are given in Table 1. The effect of solvents on the reaction

has been studied and the results are reported in Table 2. In the reaction catalysed by diethylcyclohexylamine, the rate increased with increasing K_a values of the phenols. This may be attributed to acid-catalysis as well as to the increasing ease of complexation with the decreasing acidity of the conjugate base. However the trend in the dibutyltin dilaurate catalysed systems is different. Here the methyl substituent at *meta*- and *para*-positions increases the reactivity of the phenol and decreases the activation energy. This may be due to the higher nucleophilicity of the phenol which is easily capable of reacting with the electrophilic carbonyl carbon of the NCO group. The slight decrease

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR PHENOL-PHENYL ISOCYANATE REACTION CATALYSED BY DIETHYLCYCLOHEXYLAMINE (0.002M) AND DIBUTYLTIN DILAURATE (0.0002M) IN BENZENE

[Phenol] = [Phenyl isocyanate] = 0.2M.

Phenol	K_a	Second order rate constant, $k \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$			E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		31°	40°	50°		
<i>Diethylcyclohexylamine</i>						
Phenol	1.1×10^{-10}	1.995	3.447	4.672	36.8	-183.28
<i>o</i> -Cresol	0.63	0.815	2.001	3.113	59.8	-114.30
<i>m</i> -Cresol	0.98	1.539	2.949	5.228	53.1	-132.47
<i>p</i> -Cresol	0.67	0.962	2.465	4.672	57.4	-120.24
<i>Dibutyltin dilaurate</i>						
Phenol	1.1×10^{-10}	4.300	9.462	14.34	66.2	-80.93
<i>o</i> -Cresol	0.63	4.313	8.993	12.86	62.4	-93.40
<i>m</i> -Cresol	0.98	5.998	10.966	17.31	59.8	-100.15
<i>p</i> -Cresol	0.67	6.393	11.488	18.37	57.4	-107.44

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENTS ON REACTIVITY OF PHENOL WITH PHENYL ISOCYANATE

[Phenyl Isocyanate]=[Phenol]=0.2 M, Temp. = 31°

Solvent	Dielectric constant*	DN*	Hydrogen bonding index*	Catalyst DBTDL mol dm ⁻³	k × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
	ε		γ		
Dioxane	2.21	14.8	9.7	0.000 2	0.815
Acetonitrile	38.8	—	6.3	0.000 2	0.966
				0.000 1	0.683
Benzene	2.28	0.1	0	0.000 2	1.248
Toluene	2.38	—	4.5	0.000 2	1.248
DMF	36.7	26.6	11.7	0.000 05	1.539

*Data taken from Ref. 6; DN=electron donor number.

observed for *o*-cresol may be due to steric hindrance. The higher negative entropy of activation for the reaction catalysed by diethylcyclohexylamine indicates the formation of a rigid association complex between the reactant and the catalyst in the transition state. The association complex of phenols with tertiary amine bases have been reported^{3,4}. On increasing the OH/NCO ratio for the phenol-phenyl isocyanate reaction, a first order behaviour was observed and at all other ratios the reaction followed the second order kinetics. This is in contrast to the observations of Furkas and Strohm² who reported deviations even at very low reactant concentrations in the presence of the triethylenediamine catalyst.

The solvent effect on the reaction of phenyl isocyanate and alcohols has been studied^{5,6}. Kresta *et al.*³ reported that the rate of the phenol-phenyl isocyanate reaction increases on changing the

solvent from dioxane to toluene and then to DMF. Similar results were observed in the present investigation. The reactivity increased in the following order: dioxane < acetonitrile < benzene=toluene < DMF. In the DMF medium the reaction was too fast for measurement and hence the catalyst concentration had to be reduced four times. The dielectric constant or the electron donor number or the hydrogen bonding index individually appears to have no effect on the rate. Acetonitrile with a possibility of coordination shows a negative effect on the rate while the DMF with a slightly lower dielectric constant and similar coordinating power has an exceedingly positive effect on the rate which warrants deeper study.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Indian Space Research Organisation for financial assistance.

References

1. D. S. TARBELL, R. C. MALLATT and J. W. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2229; J. W. BAKER and J. GUANT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 19; J. BURKUS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 474; H. KOTHANDARAMAN and A. S. NASAR, *Bull. Soc. Kinet. Ind.*, 1990, 12, 3.
2. A. FURKAS and P. E. STROHM, *IEC Fund.*, 1965, 4, 32.
3. J. E. KRESTA, A. GRACIA, K. C. FRISCH and G. LINDEN, *ACS Symp. Ser.*, 1981, 172, 403.
4. J. R. HULETT, J. A. PEGG and L. G. SUTTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3901.
5. S. EPHRAIM, A. M. WOODWARD and R. B. MESROBAIN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 1326.
6. M. C. CHANG and S. A. CHEN, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A*, 1987, 25, 2543.